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Prevention of fraud based on spirituality in village credit institutions in Badung Regency

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Abstract

LPD is a traditional village-based microfinance institution in Bali that provides financial access in the form of credit for small businesses, traditional and religious activities. There are several problems that are currently threatening LPD like internal fraud, poor financial performance, and difficulty handling problem loans. This research explores using spirituality-based fraud prevention fraud hexagon theory and theory of planned behavior with informants selected through purposive sampling and multilocation case studies. The research results show that spirituality has been applied in preventing fraud in LPD. The causes of fraud can be prevented through a simple lifestyle, financial transparency, fair salary standards, employee rotation, recognition of employee character, and supervision. Theory of planned behavior shows that integrity, responsibility, compliance with SOPs, fair social norms, and spirituality strengthen self-confidence in preventing fraud. The practice of spirituality increases peace of mind, reduces stress, and improves performance through the meaning of life and the benefits of prayer. This research strengthens the fraud hexagon theory and increases employee awareness about self-control and a work culture based on spiritual values.

Keywords: Prevention Fraud; Fraud Hexagon Theory; Spirituality; Case studies

1. Introduction

Financial institutions are institutions that play a role in facilitating financial activities in society and play an important role in circulating the flow of money in the economy. Financial institutions consist of two types, namely bank financial institutions and non-bank financial institutions. Bank financial institutions include commercial banks, central banks, and Rural Banks (BPR). Meanwhile, non-bank financial institutions are institutions whose establishment aims to help improve community welfare, such as Village Credit Institutions (LPD).

LPD is the only traditional village-based microfinance institution in Bali proposed by the Governor of Bali, namely Prof. Ida Bagus Mantra with the main aim of improving the welfare of traditional village communities through integrated and sustainable socio-economic activities. This microfinance institution is run based on Hindu customs in its management system, but has been managed professionally based on a modern banking system in its technical operations. This added value then makes LPDs in Bali superior to existing formal financial institutions (Tri et al., 2021).

The contribution of LPDs in encouraging the village economy provides positive value as can be seen from the existence of LPDs which as of December 2020 were recorded as having total assets of Rp. 26.3 Trillion. However, in 2022, based on the National Discussion held by the LPD Care Media Forum on February 17 2022 in Denpasar, it can be seen that there will be a decline in assets so that LPD's total assets will be Rp. 23.5 trillion due to the Covid-19 pandemic and coupled with failures in LPD management which resulted in several LPDs going bankrupt. The positive contribution of LPDs is not comparable to the number of LPDs that have gone bankrupt or are not developing well in Bali. This is clear from records showing that several LPDs experienced problems and even went bankrupt (Gayatri et al., 2022).

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In practice, there are many challenges and obstacles that hinder the implementation of LPD, especially the pandemic that hit Bali, which of course affects the progress of LPD. These problems include LPDs that are not operating, LPDs with inadequate financial performance, difficulty handling problem loans, and deviant acts such as fraud. The unhealthy nature of the LPD is caused by the high level of fraud committed by the LPD itself which is caused by opportunity, abuse of authority and lack of responsibility. supervision of employees (Erika & Indraswarawati, 2022).

Fraud is an illegal act characterized by deception, concealment, or breach of trust. This is also explained by Sari & Mahyuni (2020) that the existence of fraud or cheating in an organization will disrupt the running of the organization and even have the potential to destroy the organization. In financial institutions, especially LPDs, fraud not only causes financial losses but also causes the village community's confidence in saving their funds in LPDs to decrease. In order to avoid these losses, the LPD must be able to make improvements to avoid fraud by means of a commitment between stakeholders (Pakraman village community, Pakraman village administrators and LPD managers) to protect the LPD to avoid detrimental behavior (fraud).

Some example of a fraud case that occurred at LPD is abuse of authority committed by the former chairman of the Ungasan Traditional Village LPD, corruption committed by the former supervisor of the Kapal Traditional Village LPD, and corruption committed by the chairman of the Ambengan Traditional Village LPD. Another example was also experienced by former chairman of the Sangeh Traditional Village LPD who used the method of creating fictitious credit, as well as corruption in the management of financial funds carried out by the chairman, secretary and treasurer of the Kekeran Traditional Village LPD.

Table 1 Data on LPD Fraud Cases Per District for 2017-2023

No	Regency	Number of Cases
1	Buleleng	8 Cases
2	Badung	5 Cases
3	Bangli	4 Cases
4	Jembrana	3 Cases
5	Tabanan	3 Cases
6	Karangasem	3 Cases
7	Gianyar	3 Cases
8	Klungkung	2 Cases
9	Kota Denpasar	1 Cases

Source: Processed data (2023)

Within the LPD, faith, management and spirituality must be strengthened. Spirituality is a trait that can differentiate good behavior from bad behavior. Spirituality influences how a person or society acts, thinks, behaves, and also influences how they make decisions. Spirituality describes the process of searching for meaning, purpose, morality, well-being and relationships with oneself and others (Urumsah et al., 2016).

Research conducted by Purnamasari & Amaliah (2015) and Purnamasari et al., (2020) conduct research on the value of spirituality in the workplace in preventing corruption, especially BPKP, to see how it impacts corruption prevention. The research results show that spiritual values strengthen and influence fraud prevention. Similar findings were also made by Budiarto & Isnaeni (2022), Kristuti et al., (2023), Pratiwi & Irwansyah (2023) which shows that spirituality influences the prevention of fraud in village funds.

Different results were found by Herlyana et al., (2017) that spiritual beliefs have a negative impact on the tendency of fraudulent management of village funds. The higher a person's confidence, the lower the possibility of fraud in managing village funds. In line with research conducted by Urumsah et al., (2016) shows that a person's spirituality and faith and cheating are not interconnected things. When someone has the intention to commit fraud, it is as if their faith and spirituality are lost within them, and someone will commit fraud without considering their faith and spirituality.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) developed by Ajzen (1991) which is a conceptual framework used to examine individual behavior by showing that individual behavior is not always in line with their attitudes. Spirituality and morality reflected in individual beliefs influence attitudes, norms, and behavioral control which ultimately influence intentions and behavior. The factors in the fraud hexagon theory are also influenced by spiritual and moral conditions. Spirituality and good morality make a person better able to withstand pressure, not take advantage of opportunities to cheat, not rationalize fraudulent actions, not be arrogant, and avoid collusion. On the other hand, low spirituality and morality can increase the tendency to commit fraud.

This research was carried out at the LPD in Badung Regency because it was in second place in cases of fraud, namely the LPD of the Kedonganan Traditional Village and the LPD of the Kapal Traditional Village. The Kedonganan Traditional Village LPD is one of the LPDs in Bali Province whose management and spiritual implementation is running well and is supported by the results of its audit, namely WTP. The LPD of Kedonganan Traditional Village in implementing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is considered good, one of which is by launching a community health service facility that synergizes with Kedonganan young people and in the field of five yadnya. Kapal Adat Village LPD is one of the LPDs that experienced a fraud case in 2020. This case caused significant losses for the LPD and the public's trust in village financial institutions decreased drastically. However, after the case was revealed, the LPD administrators of Kapal Traditional Village made great efforts to improve the management and finances of their institution by implementing a transparency strategy. Currently the Kapal Traditional Village LPD is still operating and focused on pioneering and restoring community trust.

As one of the traditional financial institutions, the Village Credit Institution (LPD) indicates that the application of spirituality in the work environment will provide happiness and prosperity so it is hoped that it can prevent deviant acts such as fraud. By implementing spiritual values, it is hoped that organizations can shape the character of employees well and prevent acts of fraud, such as fraud.

1.1. Fraud Hexagon Theory

Fraud hexagon theory is a development of the fraud triangle theory proposed by Cressey (1953) which explains three factors when someone commits fraud, namely pressure, opportunity, and rationalization. Wolfe & Hermanson (2004) updating the fraud triangle theory by adding a fourth element, namely the ability to improve fraud detection. Then Crowe (2012) re-developed this theory by changing the capability factor to competence, which has a similar meaning, and adding the arrogance factor. Vousinas (2019) continued the development of this theory by adding the element of collusion.

1.2. Theory of Planned Behavior

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) was developed by Ajzen (1991) as an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). In this theory, three main variables related to attitudes and behavior determine a person's intentions. Subjective attitudes show an individual's perception of tendencies, such as the behavior they will carry out. A person has a perspective on behavior based on a combination of their beliefs about the positive or negative results of carrying out a behavior (behavioral beliefs). Subjective norms include social perceptions of the pressure exerted by people who are considered important to the decision maker regarding performing or not performing the behavior. Perceived behavioral control is what people think about how easy or difficult it is to perform the behavior (Kartika et al., 2018). All of these variables are based on individual beliefs, which include the relationship between things or actions and perceived characteristics. This theory provides a deep understanding of how individual intentions shape behavior by understanding the complex interactions between these components (Alwahidin & Muin, 2022).

1.3. Fraud

The Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) explains that fraud is any unlawful act characterized by deception, concealment, or breach of trust. Meanwhile, the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (2016) explains that fraud is any planned or unplanned action to obtain unlawful gain for oneself or a company that violates the law or to deny the victim's rights and categorizes types of fraud with the term "The Fraud Tree" which consists of financial statement fraud, misuse of assets, and corruption.

1.4. Spiritualitas

Spirituality is a trait that can differentiate good behavior from bad behavior. Spirituality influences how a person or society acts, thinks, behaves, and also influences how they make decisions. Spirituality describes the process of searching for meaning, purpose, morality, well-being and relationships with oneself and others (Urumsah et al., 2016).

Faith and spiritual values will influence the way a person thinks and acts. Spirituality provides more general values, such as honesty and integrity, that everyone can understand and adhere to (Hayati & Nuqul, 2020).

Schreurs (2002) states that spirituality consists of three components, namely existential aspects, cognitive aspects, and relational aspects. The existential aspect involves the process of searching for true self, which is a characteristic of the actions a person takes in this area. Cognitive aspect, namely a person's effort to become more sensitive to transcendent reality through contemplating certain spiritual readings or reading literature, training the ability to concentrate. The relational aspect is the unity phase where a person feels united with God. Here, a person builds, maintains, and deepens his personal relationship with God.

2. Methods

The approach used in this research is multiple case study. Multiple case study is a research method that will carry out analysis and comparison of several individual cases. The individual cases in question are cases that have similar phenomena in different conditions and environments. Multiple case studies have the potential to produce uniform findings (literal replication) or can produce different conclusions even with anticipated causes (theoretical replication) (Yin, 2018).

The type of data used in this research is qualitative data and the primary data source is the results of interviews with informants or sources. The data collection used was a gradual interview method. Staged interviews are usually carried out in stages and the interviewer does not have to be involved in the informant's social activities (Bungin, 2017). Carrying out interviews will use informed consent, which is a concept that can provide descriptions and statements that explain the relationship between researchers and research informants. Informed consent is used to protect research informants from potential uses, losses and threats.

The informants in this research were 4 people from each LPD consisting of the LPD Chair, LPD Secretary, LPD Treasurer, and LPD Supervisory Board. Informant coding is used to differentiate informants from each LPD. The letter 'A' is used as the code for the LPD of Kapal Traditional Village and the letter 'B' is used as the code for LPD of Kedonganan Traditional Village, and the number '1' is used as the code for the first informant.

The analysis technique used in this research is pattern matching. The pattern matching technique involves pairing data collected during research with a narrative theory or condition that has been used as a reference since the beginning of the research (Yin, 2018). In this research, pattern matching techniques are used to compare patterns based on empirical data, or field data, with patterns that exist theoretically (or with several alternative predictions) (Yuliastina et al., 2020).

Researchers collected field data in the form of interviews, observations and documentation studies. The data is then analyzed and categorized based on themes relevant to the research focus. These themes are then compared with the theories and concepts used in the research to see whether the field data matches predictions based on theory or there are new findings in the field that have not been covered in the theoretical framework. These questions are answered through pattern matching techniques between field data and theory. Therefore, research results can be validated and research contributions to theory development can also be identified using pattern matching.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Fraud Hexagon Theory

Based on the results of interviews with informants, it shows that fraud prevention efforts with spirituality have been implemented at the LPD research site. This implementation is influenced by the relationship between intention and a person's attitude towards committing fraud. These factors include:

3.1.1. Pressure

Based on the results of interviews with informants, it was explained that the cause of pressure was a lifestyle that did not match one's abilities.

- [...] Lifestyle as it is and adapt it to reality. (A1)
- [...] Simple lifestyle and not excessive. (A2)
- [...] Lifestyle must match your abilities, so measure your abilities. (A4)
- [...] Life must be within one's abilities, a simple lifestyle. (B4)

Maulida & Prabowo (2023) explains that organizations can anticipate fraud by minimizing opportunities and reducing pressure from urgent financial needs. For example, by looking for information about employee lifestyles, employee debt, and providing consultations to employees.

Apart from lifestyle, other causes of fraud are economic factors and partner's demands.

- [...] Lifestyle is influenced by economic factors. (A3)
- [...] Fraud can arise from the demands of a partner who wants to live a luxurious life.

This is in line with research Pranata & Utami (2021) which states that every lifestyle will of course be related to money. The ability to control oneself over the demands of one's lifestyle is the key to avoiding the temptation to commit fraud (Pranata & Utami, 2021).

In an organization, pressure to achieve targets can influence employee behavior. So it is important for management to prioritize the welfare of its employees.

- [...] Giving targets definitely creates pressure. But dedicated people will try to meet that target. (A4)
- [...] Targets can motivate and increase the work enthusiasm of all employees. (B2)
- [...] Pressure is definitely there, but we explain the rewards and punishments for achieving targets or not. (B3)
- [...] If we give targets to employees, it will definitely cause pressure. (B4)

It is important for organizations to provide support and appreciation to employees in achieving these targets, so that they can create a healthy and productive work culture (Soedarsono & Sonhaji, 2023). This is in line with research Amaliyah (2019) namely employee welfare is important and has a positive impact on productivity and overall organizational performance.

Pressure factors such as lifestyle, economic factors, partner demands and giving targets to employees can be minimized by controlling oneself, being grateful for what one has, and establishing a relationship and communicating with God through prayer to surrender and release burdens to feel calm.

- [...] Prayer brings you closer to being calm, sincere, and releasing your burdens so you can think clearly. (B1)
- [...] The purpose of prayer is to surrender to avoid negative thoughts and things. (B3)
- [...] Prayer makes us calm, so we can work well. (B4)

3.2. Opportunity

The cause of the opportunity is weak organizational structure, supervisory function, ewuh pakewuh culture, absence of system or unwillingness to use the system, weak governance and organizational culture of LPD (Sari & Mahyuni, 2020). Based on the results of interviews with informants, opportunities can be overcome by creating openness, transparency in financial reports and supervision from supervisory bodies.

Important principle in good accounting practice is disclosure of financial information. However, the financial information submitted must be limited to internal and external financial information.

- [...] Here we use open management, both in reporting and presenting problems to employees. (A1)
- [...] We must be open to reducing opportunities for fraud to occur. (A3)
- [...] Financial reports must be submitted transparently to management and supervisory bodies. (B1)
- [...] Openness is very important, but it must be limited. (B2)
- [...] Financial reports are presented transparently to employees, supervisory bodies and the public as performance evaluations. (B4)

By opening up financial information, the public can see financial conditions clearly, thereby reducing the opportunity for fraud because inappropriate actions will be detected more quickly (Susilawati et al., 2022). The public can see financial conditions clearly with open financial information which can reduce opportunities for fraud because inappropriate actions will be detected more quickly (Susilawati et al., 2022).

If there is proper supervision and clear rules, a person tends to be more careful in acting because there are consequences for violations committed.

- [...] Supervisors play an important role so that we do not deviate from the SOP. (A3)

- [...] Supervision is carried out by SPI internally and externally so that if this culture continues to be implemented then fraud will not occur. (B1)
- [...] Good regulatory mastery is needed so that it is easy for the supervisory body to supervise us at the LPD. (B3)

Continuous supervision can help reduce a person's tendency to commit fraud (Soedarsono & Sonhaji, 2023). Sari & Mahyuni (2020) explains that Supervision by a supervisory body is needed because both LPD employees and administrators are at risk of committing fraud, so trust and openness alone are not enough to prevent it.

4. Rationalization

Rationalization involves justifying or falsifying reasons to justify actions that are actually wrong. Rationalization behavior is caused by ignorance and a way of thinking to seek opportunities for one's own interests. Based on the results of interviews with informants, the cause of rationalization was the difference in salary standards.

- [...] People often feel dissatisfied if the salary given is small and their needs are many. (A3)
- [...] Salary standards can clearly trigger fraud. However, we must be able to measure our own abilities. (A4)
- [...] Very influential. If the salary is sufficient and there is modesty, cheating will be minimized. (B2)
- [...] Salary standards can trigger fraud, so pay attention to employee welfare. (B3)
- [...] Certainly yes, because of dissatisfaction among employees. (B4)

Rationalization of fraud regarding differences in salary standards can occur when employees feel dissatisfied with the salary given or feel jealous of other employees whose salaries are higher. Buwono & Maulidi (2023) explains that dissatisfaction is often associated with complaints, demands, and expressions of feelings about difficult work.

Efforts are being made to overcome these rationalization actions, namely paying attention to employee welfare by providing adequate salaries. Amaliyah (2019) explained that it is important to pay attention to employee welfare as part of a fraud prevention strategy. One way is to ensure that salaries are given in accordance with employee contributions and performance and to reduce the possibility of fraud caused by differences in salary standards.

4.1. Capability

Capabilities refer to the abilities, skills, knowledge and resources possessed by an individual to achieve certain goals or carry out tasks effectively. It does not rule out the possibility that people who have power in an organization can make mistakes just because they have the ability. Capabilities can be overcome by working according to areas of ability, employee rotation, and disclosure of financial information.

- [...] Someone who works according to their abilities will make it easier for them to work, but that does not guarantee that they will not cheat. From time to time rolling is required. (A4)
- [...] If it is in accordance with the field and competence, we hope that fraud will not occur. (B1)
- [...] Does not guarantee that fraud will not occur. It is important to rotate employees, because the longer employees work in this field, the more they will find opportunities for fraud. (B3)
- [...] If the position is suitable, you will definitely work well, but don't take too long because cheating will be easier. So we routinely rotate employees. (B4)

Placing employees who have the ability and expertise in the right positions can reduce errors and improve overall performance. Placement of employee positions according to ability also cannot take too long, so employee rotation is needed. Engko et al., (2021) explains that it is very important to rotate employees because the longer an employee works in a position, the more likely they are to become aware of fraud opportunities.

Based on the results of interviews with informants, openness of financial information is also able to overcome capabilities. Openness of financial information can improve the ability to detect and prevent fraud. When financial information is open, all interested parties have equal access to the data and can monitor financial activity more effectively, making it more difficult for fraudsters to hide their actions (Yusuf et al., 2021).

- [...] Preventatively, we have to be open so that we know more quickly about problems that occur. (A3)

4.2. Ego

Ego is a psychological concept that refers to a person's awareness of themselves, which includes their perceptions, identities, and desires. In a company/organization, ego is usually associated with a sense of seniority/superiority. A person with high seniority and superiority may be at risk of abusing the authority given to them.

This is in line with research Soedarsono & Sonhaji (2023) that is, although feelings of selfishness and superiority themselves do not directly cause fraud, these traits can provide an incentive or opportunity for someone to damage the integrity of the organization. Ego can be overcome by getting to know the character of superiors and employees, respecting each other and not having a sense of seniority/superiority.

- [...] Knowing character is important so that minimal cheating occurs. (A3)
- [...] During a job interview we can see and get to know character. (A4)
- [...] We have to know what his personal character and even his family are like. (B3)
- [...] Get to know the environment around us so we know what their character is like. (B4)

The approach to understanding employee character is not only limited to the individual, but also their family. Because the community and surrounding environment can act as supervisors, not just LPD employees and supervisory bodies. Putri & Prasiwi (2021) explains that Organizational culture shapes employee character. Internal factors, such as individual morals, greatly influence their behavior. By understanding an individual's character and motivations, it is easier to spot risky situations and prevent them.

The sense of seniority/superiority is only limited to length of service and respect for employees who have worked longer. Seniority is also seen as a form of respect and emphasizes the importance of equality by using employee abilities to measure performance.

- [...] Seniority is important for structural respect. (B2)
- [...] Seniority is seen from the job desk and SOP. (B3)
- [...] Seniority is the length of time they have worked. Kira uses work skills to measure performance. (B4)

4.3. Collusion

Collusion is a term that refers to cooperation or conspiracy between two or more people in an organization to commit fraud. In general, collusion not only harms a company financially, but can also damage its reputation and the trust of people outside the organization, such as shareholders, investors, or other interested parties.

Based on the results of interviews with informants, Solutions can be overcome by carrying out healthy cooperation and reminding each other between employees. Working together and supporting each other makes employees create a positive work environment. Other employees will help and reprimand if they make mistakes and this encourages someone to behave honestly.

- [...] We help each other when a friend is having trouble and control each other. (A2)
- [...] Collaboration is important to help backup work for employees who are unable to attend. (A3)
- [...] Healthy cooperation and mutual reminders between employees and management. (B2)

Fraud prevention efforts in each LPD can be seen in the following table:

Table 2 Prevention Comparison Fraud at the LPD Kapal and LPD Kedonganan

Fraud Hexagon Theory	LPD Kapal	LPD Kedonganan
Pressure	LPD does the following things to reduce pressure: -Simple lifestyle -Work in a relaxed manner -Self-motivation -Giving rewards	LPD does the following things to reduce pressure: -Be professional -Live simply according to your means -Be grateful for what you have -Education regarding antifraud culture -Providing rewards and punishment

	-Tirta Yatra	-Self-motivation -Prayer to surrender and release the burden to be calm
Opportunity	LPD does the following to reduce opportunities: -Creating openness -Supervision from regulatory bodies	LPD does the following to reduce opportunities: -Transparent regarding financial reports -Supervision -Work according to the jobdesk
Rationalization	LPD does the following things to reduce rationalization: -Think positively -Believe in the law of karma -There is direction -Remind each other when they make mistakes	LPD does the following things to reduce rationalization: -Way of thinking -Sufficient salary -Work professionally -Pay attention to employee welfare
Capability	LPD does the following to suppress capability: -Employee rotation -Disclosure of financial information so that all employees know -Supervise each other and ask for consideration between employees	LPD does the following to suppress capability: -Work according to your area of ability -Disclosure of information to employees and the public -Reprimand and remind each other -Training -Employee rotation
Ego	LPD does the following things to suppress ego/arrogance: -Mutual respect -No seniority	LPD does the following things to suppress ego/arrogance: -No egocentrism -Avoid superiority and respect seniority (length of service)
Collusion	LPD does the following to suppress collusion: -Cooperation based on a code of ethics -Mutual control between employees	LPD does the following to suppress collusion: -Remind each other that there is an embedded sense of family -Healthy cooperation and mutual support

5. Conclusion

This research shows that fraud prevention efforts in LPD have been implemented through spirituality, which is influenced by elements of fraud hexagon theory, the theory of planned behavior. Factors that cause fraud, such as pressure, opportunity, rationalization, ability, ego, and collusion, can be prevented with a simple lifestyle, openness of information, and strict supervision.

Theory of planned behaviors suggests that employees' subjective views of integrity and compliance with SOPs are critical to preventing fraud. This subjective view is supported by subjective norms in the work environment that support financial justice and simple living.

Spirituality provides values such as honesty and integrity, and helps employees control themselves and reduce stress through daily spiritual practices such as prayer, which strengthens the spiritual connection with God and improves performance.

5.1. Implication and Limitation

However, this research found that there is still implementation that is not optimal, namely:

- Implementation of responsibilities is not fully in accordance with the SOP due to employees' limitations in understanding the contents of the SOP. Low control of employee behavior causes low implementation of responsibilities so that employees do not fully understand their position and responsibilities within the organization. This happens because there are limitations in recruiting employees, on the other hand, LPD has the aim of opening up employment opportunities for village people.
- There is a culture of ewuh pakewuh to reprimand employees because they think that all LPD employees are krama. Bosses feel reluctant to reprimand them because they are afraid of offending employees' feelings, thereby impacting good relations with employees. This shows that there is still low control over employee behavior and their understanding of positions and responsibilities in the organization.
- The concept of ngayah is still misunderstood, this causes employees to think that working at LPD is just community service and puts professionalism at work aside. This can reduce employees' positive attitudes towards work, reducing their motivation and responsibility at work.
- Based on the conditions found, optimization efforts that can be taken are:
 - Conduct training to increase employee understanding of the job desk and SOP. Strict employee recruitment system with fit and proper tests for leaders and sorting CVs according to employee abilities.
 - Work professionally by understanding the concept of ngayah and putting aside the ewuh pakewuh culture. It is normal to reprimand an employee if the employee makes a mistake, even if you consider the employee to be a friend or relative. Because if this culture continues, it will actually have a negative impact on the LPD.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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